

FAIR Access to Register Data

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What are register data?

Based on public registers, e.g. tax, health, crime

Gathered for administrative purposes

Some data from surveys, e.g. many data on businesses

Typically very sensitive and can hence not be shared

Differences between SD and SDS
(primary/secondary)

How do you access register data?

Access via Research Support – provide support

NEW: Danish Data Portal (implemented for all users from 3 October 2022)

Public and private users can be authorised

Provide a project description (simpler than a DMP – mainly, purpose, data needed and societal benefit)

SD: Pseudonomised access to analysis; sanctions if rules are broken

Data stays in DST – at the Research machine, on a hosted server or (soon) on an HPC-platform.

Available long before FAIR – but...

Findable

- Substantial and public metadata

Accessible

- Free data, if authorized
- Research support (for a fee)

Interoperable

- ...with other registers
- And with external data (if key variable available, e.g. CPR)

Reusable

- Definitely – thats the idea!

Room for improvement

Findable

- Not available in English
- Not easy to find, if you do not know SD/SDS

Accessible

- Students could have more access

Interoperable

- Nordic exchange is difficult

Reusable

- Easier access to information on previous projects

